

Safety Management Practice Impact on Project Performance

Anjay Kumar Mishra

* Doctoral Research Scholar, Project Management, Institute of Business Management,
Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur, India, OrcidID: 0000-0003-2803-4918;
Email: anjay_mishra2000@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

The funds allocated by the government of Nepal in transportation as the infrastructure of infrastructures and the basis of development in underdeveloped and developing countries, transportation projects hold the largest share of construction projects in Nepal. Despite of this fact, the safety and health level on the construction sites lags behind and the industry is known to be among the most dangerous to work in.

The aim of the study is to analyze the impact of occupational safety and health management practice on concerned construction project performance. The data required for this study was collected from the ongoing road construction projects of Eastern, Nepal using Questionnaire, Key-informant interview, Literature review and analyzed using Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis, Hypothesis testing using regression followed by ANOVA Test. There is impact of hazard identification on project performance followed by the impact of health facilities on project performance and there is impact of safety provisions on project performance. The safety and health also decide the duration of project and planning and scheduling. Reducing safety accidents save time and helps in successful project performance. The main goal of safety and health programs is to prevent workplace injuries, illnesses, and deaths, as well as the suffering and financial hardship these events can cause for workers, their families, and employers.

Keywords: occupational, Health, Safety, construction, Effective, Measures .etc.

Background

Construction site is full of the major physical health hazards such as noise, vibration and heat, mechanical hazards were vibration, chemical hazards were dust and asphalt fumes. Similarly, ergonomic hazards observed were poor work posture, handling of heavy hand-held tools, use of excessive work force and repetitive movements. Results revealed that cough, asthma, skin allergy, back pain, leg cramps, hearing problem, musculoskeletal problems and fatigue were the major health problems to workers on site. The socio-economic status such as low monthly income and education level as well as inadequate health determinants such as inadequate access to clean drinking water and safe food and unavailability of first aid is the additional factors causing deteriorated health conditions among workers. Non-compliance of ILO guidelines for working hours, non-use of PPE, and attitudes of contractors towards workers are also important factors to be addressed (Abrar, Cheema, Saif & Mahmood, 2017).

In most of the construction projects in Nepal, PPE is the first priority preventive and control measures instead of elimination and substitution measures. Majority of contractors have no safety plan and site-specific safety procedures and weak implementation of such plan if they have. Also, safety briefing is the major safety training that would be conducted mostly on construction projects in Nepal. Proactive preventive and control measures is still not much practiced in Nepal. Safety practice is still in traditional way of safety management like most

of the contractors provide PPE as safety measures which is last line of preventive measures and least effective too. Contractors should prioritize hazards elimination and substitution plan and procedures as first preventive and control measures and contractors should have well written safety policy and plan. The effective implementation of safety policy at site should be inspected by third party and a culture of safety audit should be established to enhance the safety practices at site.

Enactment and enforcement of labor law is vital for ensuring full and effective protection of labor welfare in construction. The research shows that the reviewed countries have developed mechanism to regulate working conditions within different labor laws, though the ability to implement these laws is still under question. Specifically, although the Palestinian labor law laid down an organic recipe governing working conditions, gaps exist due to limits in its coverage, in particular lack of legal penalties of non-compliances. The study reflects partial enforcement failure to the Palestinian Labor Law, such as overtime and payment delay. Similarly, results suggest that workers are poorly aware about the occupational safety and health rights, and due to high unemployment rate and difficult economic conditions, many employees accept to work under conditions far below the standards set by the Palestinian Labor Law (Shaaban, 2015).

Safety and Health Facilities:

The safety and health facilities are lacking in the construction site under RIP. Even though the contractor has these provisions in the contract, they hesitate to invest the extra amount of money for safety equipment. No proper monitoring from concerned authority about this was found in RIP. Workers were found untrained, unskilled, and uninformed about safety measures and equipment's to be used at road construction sites. Safety monitoring has been done monthly to check the quality assessment of the workers and their working conditions. But there was no detailed record for safety reporting and accident investigation. Generally, safety reporting is done only to the internal management. Safe drinking water and safety signs are ranked as the most important health and safety facility that need to be provided on site to the casual workers. Workers need proper instruction and planning prior starting any work to ensuring safety in construction sites (Mishra and Shrestha, 2017).

Safety and health facilities on construction project complements cost, environment, productivity, quality, schedule, and customer satisfaction. Safety and health help to reduce site accidents and losses and damages due to accidents. It helps to keep project on schedule and desire quality. Safety and health reduce variability and consequently project risk. Safety and health should be both an organizational and project value, as opposed to a priority, as priorities may change (Smallwood, 1999).

Majority of the construction site accidents can be minimized if appropriate measures are established for the promotion and protection of safety and health of the workers. Safety and health in construction is needed to minimize rate of accidents and cost of construction, to increase quality, efficiency, and morale of workers. To enhance safety practices, an emphasis must be given to enhance interests in active safety management and implementation of awareness programs, which must be developed and implemented among construction workers.

Research Objectives

The objective of this research is to analyze the impact of occupational safety and health

management practice on eastern Nepal construction project performance based on perception.

Methodology

The study is adopting the similar methods of Mishra and Malik, 2017 where impact of risk management on project success has been assessed.

Table 1. Summary of Methodology

SN	Objectives	Tools for Data Collection	Data Source	Analysis method
1.	To analyze the impact of occupational safety and health management practice on concerned construction project performance	Primary and Secondary Data	Questionnaire, Key-informant interview, Literature review	Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis,

Following hypothesis was tested to analyze the impact of OSH management practices on project performance.

Hypothesis: -

H₀₁: There is no impact of hazard identification on project performance

H_{a1}: There is an impact of hazard identification on project performance

H₀₂: There is no impact of health facilities on project performance

H_{a2}: There is an impact of health facilities on project performance

H₀₃: There is no impact of safety provisions on project performance

H_{a3}: There is an impact of safety provisions on project performance

These hypotheses were tested by using regression analysis followed by ANOVA test, which will signify whether the impact exists between independent and dependent variable.

Impact of OSH Management on Project performance

To analyze the impact of OSH management on project performance, hypotheses were tested among the independent variables and dependent variables as shown in the response table 2.

Table 2: Response related to impact of OSH Management on Project performance

No. of Respondent	Hazard Identification	Health Facilities	Safety Provisions	Mean Response on Project performance
1	4	5	5	4.67
2	4	5	5	4.67
3	3	4	4	3.67

4	4	4	4	4.00
5	4	5	5	4.67
6	5	5	5	5.00
7	5	5	5	5.00
8	5	5	5	5.00
9	5	5	5	5.00
10	5	5	5	5.00
11	5	5	5	5.00
12	5	5	5	5.00
13	4	4	4	4.00
14	4	4	4	4.00
15	4	4	4	4.00
16	4	5	5	4.67
17	4	5	5	4.67
18	5	5	5	5.00
19	5	5	5	5.00
20	5	5	5	5.00
21	5	5	5	5.00
22	5	5	5	5.00
23	5	5	5	5.00
24	5	5	5	5.00
25	5	5	5	5.00
26	5	5	4	4.67
27	5	5	5	5.00

Table 3: Reliability Statistics for data of impact of OSH Management on Project performance

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.8539	0.85	03

Here, alpha value lies above 0.8, so internal consistency of data is good.

Hypothesis Testing:

H₀₁: There is no impact of hazard identification on project performance

H_{a1}: There is an impact of hazard identification on project performance

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if there is impact exists between Hazard Identification and Project performance.

Table 4: Regression to find impact of Hazard Identification on Project performance

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.884
R Square	0.781
Adjusted R Square	0.772
Standard Error	0.199
Observations	27

<i>ANOVA</i>					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	3.527	3.527	88.954	1.030E-09
Residual	25	0.991	0.039		
Total	26	4.518			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	1.785	0.315	5.656	6.9E-06	1.135	2.435
X Variable 1	0.643	0.068	9.431	1E-09	0.502	0.783

The Examined (F) value was equal to (88.954) with possibility value (1.030E-09) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05), and that shows there is a significant impact exists between Hazard Identification and Project performance. So, the null hypothesis was not accepted: There is an impact of Hazard Identification on Project performance.

H₀₂: There is no impact of health facilities on project performance

H_{a2}: There is an impact of health facilities on project performance

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if there is impact exists between Health Facilities and Project performance.

Table 5: Regression to find impact of Health Facilities on Project performance

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.941

R Square	0.885
Adjusted R Square	0.881
Standard Error	0.144
Observations	27

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	4.000	4.000	192.999	2.92E-13
Residual	25	0.518	0.020		
Total	26	4.518			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	-0.030	0.345	-0.088	0.931	-0.739	0.679
X Variable 1	0.991	0.071	13.892	2.9E-13	0.844	1.138

The Examined (F) value was equal to (192.999) with possibility value (2.92E-13) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05), and that shows there is a significant impact exists between Health Facilities and Project performance. So, the null hypothesis was not accepted: There is an impact of Health Facilities on Project performance.

H₀₃: There is no impact of safety provisions on project performance

H_{a3}: There is an impact of safety provisions on project performance

To test this hypothesis, Regression was used to find out if there is impact exists between Safety Provisions and Project performance.

Table 6: Regression to find impact of Safety Provisions on Project performance

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.886
R Square	0.784
Adjusted R Square	0.776
Standard Error	0.196
Observations	27

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	3.492	3.492	90.917	8.307E-10
Residual	25	0.960	0.0384		
Total	26	4.453			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	0.595	0.435	1.368	0.183	-0.301	1.491
X Variable 1	0.865	0.091	9.535	8.3E-10	0.678	1.052

The Examined (F) value was equal to (90.917) with possibility value (8.307E-10) and it is lower than the specific value (0.05), and that shows there is a significant impact exists between Safety Provisions and Project performance. So, the null hypothesis was not accepted: There is an impact of Safety Provisions on Project performance.

Table 7: Summary of hypothesis testing:

S.N.	Hypothesis	F	Sig. F	Impact
1.	Impact of Hazard Identification on Project performance	88.954	1.030E-09	Impact Exists
2.	Impact of Health Facilities on Project performance	192.999	2.928E-13	Impact Exists
3.	Impact of Safety Provisions on Project performance	90.917	8.307E-10	Impact Exists

As per the result presented on table 7, the calculated F value is higher than the significant f value. Therefore, all the null hypotheses are rejected and alternative hypothesis were selected i.e.

1. There is impact of hazard identification on project performance.
2. There is impact of health facilities on project performance.
3. There is impact of safety provisions on project performance.

Major Cause of Poor Implementation of Rules and Regulations

Figure 1 reflects the main major cause of poor implementation of Rules and Regulation at construction site. 67% workers and 65% employers responded that the major cause found for poor implementation of rules and regulation was lack of safety department with adequate budget and manpower at site. The second cause found lack of inspection and monitoring from the government authority.50% workers and 45% employers responded there was lack of

inspection and monitoring from government authority. 65% employers and 24% workers responded cause for poor implementation of rules and regulations were lack of appointment of safety manager. The least major cause of poor implementation was lack of specific safety policy and plan.

Figure 1 Major cause of poor implementation of rules and regulations

As per KII, there was the safety department but no any safety engineer and safety budget was not been defined in the contract document. He also mentioned that the Rules and Regulations are sufficient but it has not been practiced in the real construction site. So to avoid the accidents the document only will not prevent the accident a regular inspection from the government authority should be pursued.

As per Foad Mohamed (2011) an international case study made on Libya about improving safety performance in construction project; the existing safety procedures, regulations, policies, and accidents prevention methods related to the construction projects; there was a consensus among the respondents that implementation of safety regulation helps in reducing accidents. Construction professionals should play more active roles in sustaining construction safety and in improving safety culture for construction workers. There was also a consensus between the respondents that responsibility for safety and health was only confined to construction work on site. There was a consensus among the respondents that special government institutions should increase their effort and participation in improving safety by organizing safety-training course for workers. There was also the delegation from the ministry of labor should visit the construction sites to follow up safety performance, and for the insurance companies to visit the sites for the insured projects.

Activities to be Carried for Safety in the Construction Sites

Construction work is one of the most dangerous professions. And work on the job site is where most accidents occur. Employers do need to mitigate safety hazards to construction

workers, but workers need to keep in mind a lot of precautions themselves when working in such hazardous conditions. Thus, construction industry leaders must strive to safeguard their employees.

Figure 2 illustrates the results of the activities to be carried for safety in the construction site. 60% workers responded in order to prevent accident at site the main leading activity was to provide sufficient safety equipment to the workers. Secondly, 30% workers responded regular safety training should be provided to workers at the construction site. 9% workers responded the faulty equipment should not be operated and replaced from the work site. And the least activity found was appointment of the safety supervisors, only 1% workers had responded for the safety supervisors.

Figure 2 Activities to be carried for safety in the construction sites

Provision for Effective Measure to Control the Hazard at Site

Any construction site is a dangerous occupation for all personnel, especially for labors working on site and so one must be prepared every day for safety. For this purpose, various safety measures have to be taken.

According to KII, there is only few numbers of PPE available at site. Although in contract document it was mentioned that the safety falls under the contractor responsibility there was inadequate PPE at site to prevent the accidents.

The next thing observed at site was the workers used the safety helmet as equipment to transport the water at the time of brick work and plaster work. It was also found those safety helmets were used at the labor toilet for water use. In depth research on effective culture as Blair, et. al , 2003, and as Bond et al.. (2004) regarding Gendered work conditions, health, and work outcomes followed by Buchholz, (1996) related to work sampling-based approach

to ergonomic job analysis for construction and other non-repetitive work and other activities should be focused to ensure safety.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions were drawn along with suggestions;

The construction industry is considered as one of the very often hazardous industrial sectors where the construction is more led to accidents. However, occupational safety and health in construction industry is very poor in developing countries like Nepal because lack of safety regulations and standards, lack of safety training, lack of safety awareness and safety management systems which leads to delay in construction project planning and scheduling process. The hazard identification, safety and health facilities are very important in construction industry and it must be maintained in construction industry to save risks and a healthy construction environment. The safety and health also decide the duration of project and planning and scheduling. Reducing safety accidents save time and helps in successful project performance. The main goal of safety and health programs is to prevent workplace injuries, illnesses, and deaths, as well as the suffering and financial hardship these events can cause for workers, their families, and employers. The recommended practices use a proactive approach to managing workplace safety and health. Traditional approaches are often reactive –that is, problems are addressed only after a worker is injured or becomes sick, a new standard or regulation is published, or an outside inspection finds a problem that must be fixed. These recommended practices recognize that finding and fixing hazards before they cause injury or illness is a far more effective approach.

Recommendation for further research

1. Assessing the determinants of the workers' perception on the construction safety.
2. Exploring the association between socio-demographic and other individual characteristics of workers with their perception on construction safety.
3. Listing the common causes of accidents on the construction projects and rank them best on workers' perception.
4. Assessing the major hazards at construction of big projects like airport, railway and hydropower etc.
5. Assessing the safety practices adopted at construction of big projects.
6. To evaluate the effectiveness of safety measures adopted site.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my deepest thanks to all the helping hands without which this work would not have been completed. This research is dedicated to all the faculty of Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur, India from engineering and management department. Assoc. Prof. Dr. N.K. Shing and Prof. Dr. Kameshwar Mishra who has enlighten me to

complete this work. I can't forget contribution of Prof. Mukesh Sir and Prof. J.V. Sir contribution.

References

- [1] Abrar, A., Cheema K.J., Saif, S. & Mahmood, A. (2017). Health Status Assessment of Workers During Construction Phase of Highway Rehabilitation Projects Around Lahore, Pakistan. *Journal of Occupational Health*. 59 (1). Pp 74-80.
- [2] Mishra, A.K. and Mallik, K. (2017). Factors and Impact of Risk Management Practice on Success of Construction Projects of Housing Developers in Kathmandu, Nepal. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)*, 36, pp. 206-232.
- [3] Mishra, A.K. and Shrestha, M. (2017). Health and Safety Status of Casual Workers in Road Improvement Project in Kathmandu Valley, Nepal. *International Journal of Engineering Technology Science and Research*, 4(9), pp. 1187-1199.
- [4] Shaaban, N.N. (2015). Reflection on Labor Law- Construction Industry Between Text and Application. *Global Journal of Politics and Law Research*, 3, 1, Pp 55-70.
- [5] Smallwood, J. (1999). The Role of Health and Safety in Project Management. Project Management Institute South Africa. Edited Conference Presentations.
- [6] Smallwood, J., Haupt, T. and Shakantu, S. (2008). Construction health and safety in south Africa: Status and recommendations. CIDB report.
- [7] Foad Mohamed Al-Kilani (2011), IMPROVING SAFETY PERFORMANCE IN CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS IN LIBYA (CASE STUDY: IN TRIPOLI CITY)
- [8] Blair, E. Effective Safety Cultures: Myths, Magic, and Reality. In Proceedings of the ASSE Professional Development Conference and Exposition, Denver, CO, USA, 22–25 June 2003.
- [9] Bond MA, Punnett L, Pyle JL et al.. (2004) Gendered work conditions, health, and work outcomes. *J Occup Health Psychol*; 9: 28–45
- [10] Buchholz, B.; Paquet, V.; Punnett, L.; Lee, D.; Moir, S. PATH: A work sampling-based approach to ergonomic job analysis for construction and other non-repetitive work. *Appl. Ergon.* 1996, 27, 177–187.